

HISTORICAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF WOMEN'S SERVICE IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: This scientific article examines the historical and legal foundations of women's service in the internal affairs bodies of Uzbekistan. It analyzes normative-legal changes from the Soviet period to modern reforms. The issues of women's employment, legal protection, and gender inequality are considered. The research utilizes archival documents, laws, and statistical data. The aim is to provide a scientific basis for the legal development of women's service activities and to offer proposals for future reforms.

Keywords: women, internal affairs bodies, historical and legal foundations, gender inequality, regulatory framework, service activities.

The system of service in internal affairs bodies has historically developed in close connection with the progress of society and the formation of state administration. In the system of statehood, the tasks of ensuring citizen safety, maintaining public order, and preventing offenses have always been of great importance. Consequently, the system of internal affairs bodies and the procedure for serving in it began to be based on specific legal foundations.

The traditions of service in the territory of Uzbekistan have ancient roots. Notably, during the reign of Amir Timur, strict disciplinary rules for military and administrative service were established, along with a service hierarchy and a system of responsibility. In this system, the functional duties, accountability, and loyalty of servicemen to state interests were especially valued. During the Timurid era, women also played a certain role in public life, with sources mentioning their participation in state affairs and, in some cases, their service in administrative positions.

During the Soviet era, the internal affairs system was reorganized as an integral part of the unified state apparatus. The procedure for service through the "People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs (NKVD)," established in 1918, was implemented based on unified administrative rules. Certain changes were also observed in the policy regarding women's activities: from the 1940s-1950s, women began to serve in internal affairs bodies in specific areas - in investigation, personnel, healthcare, and administrative affairs. However, this activity was mainly limited to auxiliary and administrative functions.

After Uzbekistan gained independence, the system of service in the internal affairs bodies was fundamentally reformed. Since 1991, important steps have been taken to legally regulate the activities of the internal affairs system based on national legislation. The Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies," adopted in 2016, defined the legal, organizational, and social guarantees of service. This law also legally strengthened the activities of female employees, including guaranteeing equal opportunities, labor, and social protection at the legislative level.

In particular, in recent years, as a result of increasing the legal activity of women and strengthening state policy regarding their participation in public administration, the number of female employees in the internal affairs system has increased, and opportunities for improving

their professional qualifications and appointing them to leadership positions have expanded. Today, the improvement of service procedures is directly related not only to the improvement of general legislation, but also to the creation of favorable working conditions, social guarantees, and a system of service growth for female employees.

Thus, the procedure for serving in the internal affairs bodies has historically gone through several stages, and its modern form was formed as a result of the harmonization of national statehood traditions, international legal criteria, and the policy of gender equality in society. In this process, the scientific analysis of historical experience forms an important scientific and practical basis for improving the service system.

According to the legal scholar Kh. Boboev, before the introduction of Islam in the territory of Uzbekistan and the establishment of Sharia rules, the issues of crime and punishment were regulated in the book "Avesta"¹⁰. For example, the Vendidad section of the Avesta also regulates the application of punitive measures against individuals who commit crimes (offenses). In particular, from the Avesta, one can see that the following system of punishment existed in the teachings of Zoroastrianism:

- a) death penalty;
- b) imprisonment;
- c) corporal punishment;
- d) atonement for sin; e) blood feud.

Also, according to Zoroastrian beliefs, the punishment of flogging was widely used in the Avesta when imposing punishment for offenses against the person. In particular, in the 4th Fargard (chapter) of the Vendidad section of the Avesta, it is shown that whoever beats someone and causes them harm will be whipped for the first time thirty times with a whip, thirty times with a switch, for the second time fifty times with a whip, fifty times with a switch, for the third time seventy times with a whip, seventy times with a switch.

At the same time, according to Zoroastrian beliefs, the Supreme Court - the Council of Zoroastrian Elders - also had a special influence in the appointment of punishment to a person, and the decisions made by the Council of Elders, consisting of eight units of elders in ancient Sapallitepa, played an important role in ensuring security and law and order¹².

It should be noted that today we cannot say that all components of legal culture are being perfectly implemented in society. In this regard, it is necessary to form the legal culture of citizens and the basic characteristics that encourage them to live in a spirit of law-abidingness.

In the process of improving the service system in the internal affairs bodies, the legal consolidation of women's activities was carried out in stages. Since the second half of the 1990s, ensuring gender equality in Uzbekistan has been defined as one of the priorities of state policy. As a result of this policy, a system of legal, organizational, and social guarantees for women's service activities began to be created in the internal affairs system.

The Law "On Guaranteeing Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men," adopted in 2004, created the legal basis for gender equality. This law guarantees equal access for women to public service, including in internal affairs bodies, and serves to improve working conditions, expand opportunities for professional growth, and promotion to leadership positions.

At the same time, the system of regulatory legal acts regulating the activities of women in the internal affairs system has been gradually developed. For example, the internal service charters of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, regulations and instructions on personnel policy

established working conditions, service regime, material and social guarantees for female employees, as well as benefits related to pregnancy or childcare.

As a result of the reforms carried out during the years of independence, the legal status of women in the internal affairs bodies has been strengthened, and their number has also increased. If in the early 1990s women constituted a relatively small part of the total personnel in the internal affairs system, then by the 2020s their number had increased significantly. In this regard, the decrees and resolutions of the head of state aimed at supporting women, developing their leadership potential, and strengthening their role in public administration were of great importance.

In particular, the Presidential Decree "On Comprehensive Support for Women and Strengthening the Institution of the Family," adopted in 2019, and the Resolution "On Further Improvement of State Policy in the Field of Ensuring Gender Equality and Protecting the Interests of Women," adopted in 2021, brought reforms in this area to a new level. Based on these documents, a system has been introduced to stimulate the activities of women in the internal affairs system, organize special training programs for them, and include them in the reserve of managerial personnel.

Thus, the procedure for serving female employees in the internal affairs bodies has undergone a multi-stage evolution in the process of its historical development. From the ancient traditions of statehood to the period of post-independence reforms, this system always had a legal basis. In particular, as a result of legislative reforms carried out on the basis of the principle of gender equality and the building of a democratic state governed by the rule of law, the activities of women are not only legally guaranteed, but also practical mechanisms have been created to enhance their role in the service.

Thus, the historical development of the procedure for serving in the internal affairs bodies reflects not only the formation and improvement of the system, but also the process of raising the socio-legal status of female employees. This will serve as an important scientific and practical basis for further improvement of the service system in the future

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